

Modular software platform design for supporting a Circular Supply-Chain

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Abstract

In a circular economy system two main types of actors can be differentiated: stakeholders and end-users. Stakeholders are those who are involved in designing, manufacturing and re-processing materials, parts and products to keep them in the circular supply chain as long as possible. End users are those who use the final product for the purpose it has been designed for and once the end of life has arrived have to decide which is the path to be followed by the product. For a circular economy model to succeed, the sharing and exchanging of information between the different actors are needed. A proper design stage considering manufacturers, recyclers and disassemblers feedback as well as user expectations is crucial to create a circular product, and this happens with all the stages the product go through. In this paper, a platform to achieve the data interconnection between stakeholders and end-users is presented. This platform includes a SQL Database, an innovative Quality Assurance System, a Tracking, Labelling and Reverse Logistics System, a Decision Support System and an End-user and Stakeholder platform. The Database Management System will enable the collection, analysis and store of performance and operational data obtained from product designs, manufacturing, services, logistics and (re-)manufacture and recycle processes as well as data for material stream flows, composition and effectiveness of technologies for material production. Also, it support services for the final users, such as feedback surveys and the sustainability of the products, The services will tackle process integration for characterising the complex interactions between unit operations systems and will enable the generation of predictive engineering models to guide process optimization, process control, resources use and closing the entire loop. The Quality Assurance System and the Decision Support System will enable stakeholders to process the data produced in the supply chain and provide quality standards and support to the path decision a product should follow to efficiently close the loop. Reverse logistics options to collect products at its end of life and distribute them among stakeholders will be included and all the information regarding product history and properties will be available in an innovative labelling system. An End-user and stakeholder platform will provide access to the specific services such as logistics, decision support, quality assessment and materials information and feedbacks, linking relevant stakeholders along with the supply and value chain. The platform presented above is developed as a modular solution consisting of three blocks: Database, User Interfaces and Algorithmic. This structure enables the customization of any of the blocks, adding or modifying functionalities to suit a wide range of circular economy situations. This modular software platform will favour upgrade, refurbishment, re-use and recycling of products, parts and materials minimizing the leakage from the circular supply chain. It will bring the end-user closer to design, production, service, collection and end of life phases. It is an effective tool to introduce the circular economy model into nowadays society and will help to create circular thinking of products and materials enhancing second life options of the discard product that still has value for the supply chain and the economy.

Keywords: Supply chain management, Circular economy, Data management, Decision Support System

1. Introduction

The current dominant economic development model for production and consumption is based on the continuous use of primary resources. This model is usually called ‘take, make and dispose’ (Ness, 2008) and is rising concern regarding resources security, ethics, safety and emission production. With the continuous economic growth, it is crucial to assure resources availability and decrease import dependencies. Moreover, social and administrative trends show a burden in the ecology of the system, including preservation of material resources instead of its consumption and enhancing to close the loop of the linear supply chain and transform it into a circular economy (CE) model.

CE aims to balance economy, environment and society by minimizing the resource input, waste, emissions and energy leakage. These is being assessed nowadays by developing suitable designs that enable modularity and long-life, promoting maintenance, repair, reuse, remanufacturing, refurbishing and recycling instead of disposal and creating and industrial symbiosis that facilitate the flow of material, parts and products along the circular supply chain. Although the CE model has been theoretically analysed and several definitions and approaches have been settled, the worldwide implementation is still in its early stages. Nowadays, CE applications focus on recycling material for the same purpose it was designed for or not, which does not comply with the expectations given to CE. In Gibbs and Deutz (2007) the implementation gap of the theoretical industrial ecology and what has been achieved is analysed. The study reaches to the conclusion that for the CE to be feasible it has to be financially viable. Even though the importance of the environment and the social pressure, the most important factor in a CE project is its economic success. In Stahel (2016), the results of a report done for seven European nations are shown, which finds out that a shift to a circular economy would reduce greenhouse-gas emissions up to 70% and grow in workforce by about 4%, enabling thus economic growth of industries and countries. In Ghisellini et al. (2016) it is stated that to achieve these benefits, adoption of cleaner production patterns at company level, an increase of producers and consumers responsibility and awareness is needed. However, company level changes are not enough to attain a CE model. CE needs co-operation between the different stakeholders of the supply chain to link their process and create and industrial symbiosis. It requires a broader look at the design of the products and over the entire life cycle including the network of local stakeholders that help to encourage environmental networking through forming mutual trust (Tseng et al., 2018).

In this paper, a modular software platform is proposed as a critical tool needed to implement CE in today’s society. This platform aims to solve the problems that create the gap between the theoretical approach and the real implementation of CE. Through the different services that form it, the platform will engage actors of the circular supply chain, will gather information about materials, processes and standards to allow an industrial symbiosis between stakeholders, will create a local network of retailers and producers, will make easier the end user engagement and will assess the economic success of circularity by analysing life extension options considering reverse logistics and processes costs and benefits through a decision support system.

2. Methods

The objective of this paper is to present a modular software platform that enables the overcoming of present drawbacks for the real implementation of circular economy models. The first step to achieve the purpose is a bibliographic research to evaluate the existent barriers in today’s society. Secondly, an analysis is done and solutions for surpassing these barriers are proposed. These solutions are services aimed at the end-user and

stakeholders of the supply chain, which can be deployed through a well-known mature technology. Thirdly, a case study is presented. This case study aims at verifying the ideas of the introduced solutions into a real case scenario. This is located in Italy, specifically in the furniture sector, as it is a sector that is being governmental encouraged to perform CE activities. The background of the furniture sector in this country is studied in detail to understand the present stakeholders and the supply chain. Interviews are performed with manufacturers and material suppliers to identify the key aspects for the deployment of CE business models and to narrow down the software services to the specific problems of the sector. The software modules are developed with constant feedback from stakeholders to assure its suitability to overcome barriers and ease the use and return of products. Last of all, the up to date results and the expected trends regarding the deployment of the full platform into the sector are exposed and conclusions are drawn.

3. Circular supply chain actors

The engagement of the different actors present into the circular supply chain is crucial for the success of the implementation of CE. These actors can be divided into two big categories: stakeholders and end-users. End-users are those who benefit from the product for its intended use. They can be the owners of the product or can be using it under a leasing contract. Stakeholders are those who perform an action to the product and are in charge of the different stages of the supply chain. Stakeholders can be further subdivided according to the stage they belong to. In Kalmykova et al. (2018) and Winans et al. (2017), a review of CE theories, practices and current applications is done. After analysing them and compare the situation they present with the direct supply chain and the CE concept, the stages of the circular supply chain and the flow of materials, parts and products can be identified as shown in Figure 1. The stakeholders that appear are designers, manufacturers (material, parts and products), retailers, collectors and waste disposal agents. The role of designers influences in the development of CE as the product have to be thought to enable life extension options and circularity paths. In the case of manufacturers, its main task remains unchanged, but they have to introduce into their process materials, parts and products coming from unusual sources, such as recycled materials, spare parts from used products, final products with damages, etc. Retailers, which are in charge of distributing products for its use, will have to handle with used products and enable a second use by performing minor changes through maintenance, repairing and upgrading. Waste disposal agents act, as nowadays, in the end of life of products and are responsible of the disposal of it or, if possible, its usage for energy recovery. It has to be noted that between the end-user and the waste disposal agent there is a new stakeholder, the collector, who decides the path to be followed by the product and enables it to return to the supply chain instead of sending it to the disposal actor. The collector receives the product once the user wants to dispose it and decides, depending on the situation of the product, the market, governmental incentives and social perspectives, the path to be followed by the used product trying to minimize leakage of the chain to the waste disposal stage.

Figure 1: Resources flow in the circular supply chain.

For the different stakeholders to be able to introduce the proposed changes into their processes, the exchange of material and product related information is a decisive factor. The material manufacturer has to know the quality and composition of the circular supplied material sourcing in order to be able to produce materials with desired characteristics. The same happens with parts, product manufacturers and collectors. The collector needs to have a traceability of the product, it has to identify the state of the product and the possible sites and technical capacities to state the optimal solution for specific products. Thus, it is possible to state that information exchange has to take place and industrial symbiosis needs be settled in order to introduce CE business models into nowadays society.

4. Information to overcome circular economy barriers

The exchange of data has an important role into the development of CE. Nowadays, this exchange of information is often limited by several nontechnical barriers. In Golev et al. (2015) these barriers are identified and can be classified into: commitment to sustainable development, presence of economic benefits, community cooperation and information security and privacy. The rise of the commitment to sustainable development has to be considered a slow social process which is based in the innovation of the system. Governance is a key factor towards sustainable commitment, providing structures, practices, guidance and coordination to involved actors (Kemp et al., 2006). Although the grow of sustainable commitment is important for developing circular economy business models, an economic profit should be present for actors to apply these ideas. The economic assessment differs from the computation of the cost for the ‘take, make, dispose’ model. Apart from usual process, logistics, raw material cost, packaging, reverse logistics, time effort and cost of take-back strategies to recover the used product should be considered. The circularity of products will depend in the result of the economic evaluation between new products against recovered ones. In order to perform this assessment, there should be an exchange of information between stakeholders of the supply chain. The actor who performs the take-back strategy decision, which is the collector, should consider the cost of processes of relevant manufacturers, cost of raw material, selling price of second-hand products, etc. There is a big concern regarding the security and the privacy of the information that should be exchanged to make circularity possible, as it

should be accessible to the interested stakeholders in the supply chain. To allow a secure transfer of data, the exchange platform should be implemented as a secured database with available information depending on the user type and role and with proper design and implementation stages that impedes design flaws, data corruption, overloads and malware infections. However, the implementation of a database for information exchange would not be enough for the success of CE models. Different stakeholders should be encouraged to cooperate between them. For this reason, in this paper the database is accompanied by a set of services that facilitate the communication between actors, supporting the symbiosis for circularity. These services are related to the quality assurance of materials, parts and products created from raw and recycled materials and parts, a decision support system that evaluates the different possibilities with different stakeholders to provide optimal paths, a logistic platform to plan the complex network for taking back used products and end-users and stakeholders platforms to allow exchange of information and direct communication between actors in the supply chain.

Thus, the software platform presented in this paper will assess these barriers and will help in overcoming them. To do so, in Table 1, the information that has been identified as needed and that would help to settle a CE model for each stakeholder and end-user is shown. This information will be provided to the interested actor directly from a database or through the implementation of one of the services of the modular platform.

Table 1: Stakeholders and end-users information requirements.

CE actor	Information needs
Designer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental value - Social value - Economical profit along the supply chain - Product leakage - End-user feedback
Material producer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design - Raw material characteristics - Recycled material characteristics
Manufacturer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design - Material sourcing information - Material characteristics - Remanufacturing/Refurbishment process guidelines - Used product characteristics
Distributors and retailers-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability - Product characteristics - Maintenance/repairing process guidelines - Eco label of product
Collector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product characteristics - Failure modes - Economical cost of processes and expected benefits - Retailers & manufacturers locations

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Retailers & manufacturers possibilities and capacity - Market acceptance of products - Environmental impacts of possible circular paths - Governmental incentives of possible circular paths
Waste disposal agent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product characteristics - Legal restrictions - Governmental incentives
End-user	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Traceability - Eco label of product - Product characteristics - Repairing/maintenance process guidelines - Local network options

5. ICT Tools

From the barriers identified in the previous sections, there are two that are particularly critical to enable the circular economy principles: the information exchange between the actors involved in the supply chain and the cooperation between business. The software platform presented here is envisioned as a group of services intended to tackle these barriers enhancing the communication between stakeholders and provide additional tools to facilitate the development of a CE chain. Hence, each of the services implemented responds to a necessity of the CE or tries to lower the effect of its barriers.

5.1. End-User & Stakeholder Platform

The end-user and stakeholder platform objective is specially meant to address the aforementioned drivers by means of implementing some functionalities like, for example, the creation of a dedicated online marketplace where both the end-users and the manufacturers can buy and sell their goods or the development of local stakeholder networks offering on-demand collection alternatives and new supply streams. It also contains a space dedicated to social news, minor reparation manuals and, questions and answers intended to fight against the lack of community awareness, which is also commonly identified as a CE barrier (Rizos et al., 2016).

Additionally, the end-user and stakeholder platform serves as a common entry point to all the others services and applications. Therefore, one of its main functionalities is to hold the authentication and user role information and redirect the traffic to the exposed applications. This architecture based on a single entry point has the advantage that the user and data security is handled in a centralized manner, reducing its costs and increasing the scalability of the whole system.

5.2. Database System

All the information generated and managed by the platform services has to be stored in a common repository enabling an easy interoperability between them and promoting the data sharing between the stakeholders. Therefore, the database is the main core of the software system since it stores the data collected and generated

through the product life. This data has to be accessible to the stakeholders involved in the supply chain allowing them to modify the details of the products and it is crucial in order to decide which path is the optimal when a product is disposed by its end-user due to the fact that the decision taken will be driven by information like the product's material composition or the location of the product.

The aim of the database is then to offer a common repository to the software platform where all the product related information can be stored safely and accessible to all the interested actors enabling a network between them. This network is then supported by the tools that consume the information contained in the database in order facilitate the development of a circular supply chain. However, in addition to the global system's database, there is some information that is only related to a specific service like the rules extracted in case of the quality assurance system or the impacts used in the algorithm of the decision support system. Therefore, the data system must be compound not only by the main database but also by some service dedicated databases.

5.3. Tracking and Logistics Systems

Having a fast and reliable way to identify a product is critical for the correct operation of the tools proposed in this modular platform. The software systems described below make use of the product details as their inputs, so it must exist one system used to enable the product's traceability providing a unique identifier for each of them; linking the product with information like its origin, supply chain, material composition, technical and safety datasheets or applicable quality standards among others. This system, in addition to supply the inputs for the other tools, it is useful to engage the end-users with the CE principles since it also allows them to accurately know all the details about the product they are going to acquire and helps the manufacturers allowing them to show the benefits of circular economy and addressing the misperception that circular goods are of lower quality than traditional ones.

In the market, the most promising solutions for the labelling systems are the Quick Response (QR) codes and Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) due to their low cost when compared to their alternatives. The latter, based on the wireless use of electromagnetics fields present in tags attached to objects, has some advantages over QR codes or barcodes such as the higher amount of information it can handle, the uniqueness of all the RF identifiers or the fact that it does not require a line of sight to read the tagged items. These advantages have led to numerous attempts to implement (or study the implementation) RFID as a product passport tracking in supply chains (Dukyil et al., 2018; Tsao et al., 2017). However, they usually fail due to the high implementation and operation costs, and technology limitations when compared to QR codes. Whereas RFID tags require specific devices to access the information, anyone with a smartphone can read the information contained in a QR code. Although QR codes technology has lower barriers for its adoption since it does not require any sophisticated equipment (the code can be directly printed or carved in any kind of surface), it is also important to consider the drawbacks of these technology. The code needs to be placed in a visible and accessible spot; and this can affect drastically to the aesthetics of the product. Additionally, if the product is labelled using a sticker or the code is printed in its surface, the information contained in the code can be corrupted or damage with time making it unusable. Therefore, the manufacturer must ensure the durability of the code.

Together with the product labelling and life cycle tracking, this module has also the objective of identifying and characterize different strategies and technologies for transport and logistics optimization including a selection of suitable means of transport, payload capacity optimization, route planning, traceability, demand planning and forecasting and location of collection points and warehouses. The identified strategies are then used to support the decision making in terms of optimizing the collection, transport and logistics activities that take place along the reverse logistics supply chain of the products. The implementation of such functionality is meant to avoid another of the common barriers identified in CE projects which is the fact that some of these projects are developed in the absence of a supporting reverse logistics infrastructure leading to a traditional linear economy (Hart et al., 2019).

5.4. Decision Support System (DSS)

One of the issues that concern product manufacturers the most is how they can develop an effective management of reverse supply chain operations as the feasibility of the new business models is highly dependent on the resources spent when identifying the best recovery alternative for the returned products. This decision, which is key strategic consideration for any manufacturer or stakeholder of the circular chain, rely on information regarding time, quantity, market values, environmental impact and existing legislation. Therefore, a framework able to consider all these aspects can offer good recommendations regarding the alternative selection.

In this respect, the decision support system (DSS) is a service that enhances the cost-effectiveness of a product designed for circularity by means of providing a fast, cheap and reliable tool to evaluate the product value and its potential for recovery or remanufacture processes in order to make a proposal of the most suitable path to follow once the product arrives to the collection point. This decision-making process carried out early as the products enter the reverse supply chain can minimize the total recovery cycle. Usually, the problem that arises when trying to manage the reverse logistics supply chain is the uncertainty about the quality and value of the returned products leading to the subjectivity of the human decisions. In order to overcome this issue, in the literature, DSS applied to the end-of-life alternative selection use mathematical models based on fuzzy methodologies (Geoffrey, 2015). With objective figures such as transportation costs and market prices, DSS helps make the best decision on the optimal route that will be selected to close the circularity of the product.

5.5. Quality Assurance System (QAS)

QAS is defined as the compound of procedures and standards to be followed by the stakeholders of circular economy to assure the enforceable quality in (re-)manufacturing processes and final products. Quality evaluation processes are needed at several stages of the production and recovery of products designed for circularity. For this reason, it is important to develop a tool to ensure uniformity between lots, reduce the number of quality checks and reduce errors. The quality assurance system is a unit intended to provide informational support to the production chain and regulations for Quality Control.

The quality assurance system aims to reduce the variance between lots, assuring the conformity between supply chain steps. It is envisioned as a common repository where they can store both official standards as well as their

internal quality procedures. For this last, Quality Control Points can be defined along the circular chain to assure the accomplishment of the required quality.

6. Case study

For the validation of the different service's general functions of the modular software platform and to verify the overcoming of barriers, a case study wants to be developed. In order to implement this software platform, the existence of specific actors in the supply chain is needed. These include the presence of a collection network of stakeholders to process the recovered products, parts and materials; a stakeholder in charge of taking a decision about the path to be followed by the product and a logistic service to deploy the transport infrastructure. Some of these actors are present in specific sectors in some countries, although the behaviour of all of them for CE purposes is not deployed. In this case study it is chosen to implement the modular software platform into the furniture sector in Italy, where a wood collection network and a first degree of path decision is already engaged.

6.1. Case Definition

In Italy there exists an integrated waste management system for wood. Rilegno is the National Consortium for the collection, recovery and recycling of wooden packaging (Consorzio Nazionale Imballaggi (CONAI), 2018) which is in charge of ensuring the achievement of governmental objectives regarding wood waste recovery. Rilegno is able to close part of the loop for the circular supply chain, recycling wood materials when possible. The recovery rate of wood with this scheme is of 62.3%, being able to recycle the 54.7% of it (Garcia and Hora, 2017). This recovery rate can be broadened if, for example, a network is created between the wood waste collector, the manufacturer of the product and the material supplier. The proposed circular supply chain is shown in Figure 2. The different stages of the supply chain are assigned to involved stakeholders which are, in this case, the material supplier, the manufacturer and the waste collector. Apart of recycling, which is the reverse path implemented by the waste collector, it is proposed that the manufacturer takes part in the reverse path by taking-back its own product and perform several actions to re-introduce it to the supply chain at different stages. For doing so, the business model implemented by the manufacturer should adapt the CE necessities.

Figure 2: Circular supply chain for the furniture sector case in Italy.

As said previously, the waste collector role is already implemented nowadays. However, the decision taken by it can be improved if the DSS software services capabilities are deployed to better analyse the market trends, the recycled wood requirements and the costs and emissions produced by the energy recovery and the recycle option. The behaviour of the manufacturer is another critical point for the application of a complete circular economy model. The manufacturer could also implement several circular options at the end of the use stage of the product. In order to be able to perform a wise decision at both the wood waste collection point and at the manufacturer site, the critical points are:

- Reverse logistics and packaging: All returned products should be packed in order to allow traceability and safe transport. Reverse logistics costs should be assessed in order to see the economic feasibility of take-back strategies.
- Quality of the returned product: Previous to the reception of the product into the manufacturer's site the quality or state of it has to be estimated. A first quality-related issue will allow to identify which are the further steps in order to make the product usable again.
- Cost and time evaluation of processes: The cost and time that will be needed to fulfil each of the options of the reverse path has to be known. This should also include the possible benefit that could be obtained from the repaired/remanufactured product.

These can be solved through the modular software platform proposed. Each of the services presented in Section 5 can be assigned to one or several stages of the supply chain according to their functions and the requirements presented by the stakeholders of the circular model. The End-User & Stakeholder platform would be present along all the stages of the circular supply chain to provide support to the interested actors. The QAS could be applied in the direct chain processes, specifically in material sourcing and parts and products manufacturing. The DSS would be helpful for the decision-making process at the manufacturer site and at the wood waste

collection point. The logistics service would hang from the DSS service application, computing transportation costs to be used as a parameter for the computation of the optimal path. In the case of the database, it would not be applied to specific stages of the supply chain but serve as a base for the operation of the different services.

6.2. Technical requirements and software development

Given the complexity of the software system, a microservice-based system architecture has been adopted where the system's components are split into independent services that expose and communicate through standard APIs. This architecture solution provides several advantages over traditional monolithic approaches during the development and exploitation of the software such as the decreased downtime because the system is less prone to errors given that the logic is divided in small functional services, higher scalability as the services are deployed independently and fast iterative development due to the separation of the code bases leading to smaller, more focused implementation. Figure 3 depicts the high-level architecture, where each node represents an executable service running independently of the others, and the arrows represent the communication flow from one service to another including some example of the type of information that is exchanged between them. For the sake of simplicity, the persistence systems corresponding to specific services (DSS, QAS) have not been included as they do not exchange information to any other service.

The end-user and stakeholder platform has two different frontends. A first user interface developed as a mobile app which offers to the end-user access to the marketplace and the rest of community functionalities, and provides the product details when the label attached to it is identified. On the other hand, there is also a web-enabled frontend, where both end-users and stakeholders can access, intended to cover the functionalities related to the access to other services (i.e. Database, DSS, QAS) in addition to those included in the mobile application. The tracking and reverse logistics service will not present a graphical user interface and it will only expose a http endpoint to interact with it.

Figure 3: Microservice oriented system's architecture.

7. Discussion

The software platform presented in this paper has been adapted to a case study in the furniture sector in Italy. In this case study, all the software services are applied to specific functions and serve to one or more stakeholder of the circular supply chain. Its deployment in the sector would lead to the resolution of two main uncertainties identified. The first is the suitability of take-back strategies. The reverse logistics, the quality of the returned product and the time intervals between first and second usage of product are key aspects as they have a strong influence in the net benefit of the business model. Nowadays, the direct path involves a logistic from central points of distribution to small retailers and users. In contrast, to take-back the product it is needed to gather different products at infrequent times from distributed sources to a central collection point. In this paper, this point is being assessed by means of the Tracking and Logistics Service, which considers the location of products and its characteristics to perform cost and time computation with different transport companies to properly manage the logistics of tacking back the product. The quality of the returned product is related to the possible options for its re-introduction into the circular supply chain. This quality can be assessed through a questionnaire developed by the manufacturer and which is answered by the end-user at the end-user platform. Photos and other multimedia information would help the experts to quantify better the value of the product and its optimal circular recovering. The questionnaire would have a direct impact in the development of the functions of the DSS, which would be in charge of deciding the best from the possible paths of a specific product.

The second uncertainty identified is the potential economic benefit. Nowadays, the cost of raw material is low, so the circular supply chain has to be improved in terms of efficiency and performance to be able to obtain an economic profit from recycled material, parts and products. With the DSS, the Tracking and Reverse Logistics service it is possible to assess the different costs of the circular supply chain and compare them with the cost of virgin materials. The DSS could include not only costs of processes and materials, but also other parameters such as governmental incentives and waste taxes, which places circular options above conventional direct path approaches.

Although the case study focuses on the furniture sector in Italy, the modular software platform exposed can be applied to other sectors to facilitate a transition to circular economy. Moreover, due to its modularity, the services can be deployed strategically to solve problems and overcome barriers from specific sectors without the need to set up the whole platform. From this fact it has also to be stated that the different services, characterised by its functionalities, could be developed by different actors. For example, an enterprise could specialize in the reverse logistics and provide these services to others while communicating and creating a local network for the realization of the rest of module's functions with external partners.

8. Conclusions

The current consumption model of fast product disposal is rising concern regarding resources security, ethics, safety and emission production. For solving these problems, social and administrative trends show an increasing interest to transform the linear supply chain present until now into a CE model. CE would help to balance economy, environment and society through minimizing material leakage from a circular supply chain. The CE concept has been deeply analysed but its implementation is still in its early stage due to several technical and non-technical barriers such as commitment to sustainable development, presence of economic benefits,

community cooperation and information security and privacy. A system that enables the overcoming of these barriers and a bridge to implement CE models is needed. In this paper, a modular software platform has been presented that aims to solve the existent problems in the deployment of circular supply chains and circular business models. This platform, constituted by an End User & Stakeholder Platform, QAS, DSS, central DB and Tracking and Reverse Logistics modules; will engage actors in the supply chain and will enhance a cooperation and data exchange capabilities allowing security and privacy. Moreover, the QAS and DSS services will provide economical and efficiency assessment to assure the selection of optimal path for materials, parts and products according to the criteria specified by the interested stakeholder. The platform, which can be adapted to the needs of a specific sector or set of stakeholders, will allow a smooth transition to a CE model where economical, environmental and social aspects are considered during the different stages of the supply chain.

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